

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4 (2)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA “AKT XIZMATLARI” TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATI.....	14
Shermatov Sherzod Xotamovich RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	20
Amonov Mirzohid Tuymuratovich, Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich TIJORAT BANKLARINING BYUDJET MABLAG’LARI HISOBIGA MOLİYALASHTIRILADIGAN LOYIHALARDAGI ISHTIROKINI KUCHAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	26
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o’g’li KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO’NALISHLARI.....	33
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O’TISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI VA UNI O’ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO’LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	38
Ne’matova Mavsuma, Xolmamatov Diyorbek ВЛИЯНИЕ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ НА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННУЮ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	43
Буранова Лола Вахобовна ФИНТЕХ-ЭКОСИСТЕМА КАК ФАКТОР ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО И УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	54
Эшмуротов Дониёр Ихтиёр угли ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARI ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	60
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Matyoqub qizi, Fayzullayeva Zamira Alijonovna XIZMAT KO’RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	64
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG’OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI	
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o’g’li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	73
Abdullo Sohobov O’ZBEKISTONDA URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARI JADALLASHUVI VA UNING HUDUDIIY XUSUSIYATLARI	84
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich KORXONALAR MOLİYAVIY HOLATINI MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI (MHXS) ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	91
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o’g’li BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	95
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi O’ZBEKISTON VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA BENEFITSIAR MULKDOR KONSEPSIYASINI QO’LLASHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	100
Ochilov Farhod Malikovich O’ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O’TISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH (GDP, BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYALAR KESIMIDA).....	106
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	

INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	111
Mamatqulova Hafiza Bahodir qizi IPOTEKA BOZORI MUAMMOLARINING EMPERIK TAHLILI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	118
Olokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi MILLIY IQTISODIYOT RAQOBATIDA NAZARIY VA AMALIY QARASHLAR.....	122
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna KORPORATIV BANK XIZMATLARIGA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA ZAMONAVIY BIZNES MODELLARNI JORIY ETISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	128
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AND INDONESIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY.....	133
Ibrokhimova Iroda Ikromjon Kizi. Askolani. Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA REKRUTING AGENTLIKLARINING O'RNI.....	142
Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	148
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна BUDJET DAROMADLARI TARKIBIDAGI SOLIQLARNING ULUSHINI BOSHQARISH.....	156
Abduraxmonova Gulmira Sobir qizi RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AVTOSERVIS SHOHOVCHALARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	161
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich THE ECONOMIC NATURE OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND ITS RECOGNITION IN ACCOUNTING AS AN OBJECT OF ECONOMIC ANALYSIS.....	165
Zafar Qodirov Abdivaxobovich O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	170
Ibragimov G'ayrat Ablaqulovich. Tursunov Ozod Matlubovich Shukurova Nilufar Qahramonova IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	175
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA INTEGRAL KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	179
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS.....	184
Wang Biao USTAMA ISHLAB CHIQUARISH XARAJATLARINING MAZMUNI VA UNI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MUVOFIQ TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	190
Tashnazarova Dilfuza Samiddinovna INTEGRATSIYA SAMARADORLIGINI O'LCHASHNING METODOLOGIK MODELI VA INDIKATORLAR TIZIMI.....	195
Aliqulov Abbas Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	202
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	

MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	207
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI	213
L.S. Azimova	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING	218
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin o'g'li	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIKNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI	223
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISH ORQALI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMLARI	227
Ergasheva Zarifa Baxtiyarovna	
CHO'L-YAYLOV CHORVACHILIGI MAJMUASI RIVOJLANTIRISH	232
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich	
KREDITORLAR REYTINGINI MASHINAVIY O'QITISHGA ASOSLANGAN BASHORATLASH ALGORITMLARI	237
Beknazarov Ulug'bek Zafar o'g'li	
MIKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORI VA TALAB SHAKLLANISHI OMILLARI	242
Raximov Azizbek Saliyevich	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY Tajribasi: AQSH MISOLIDA.....	246
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARNI JORIY ETISH USULLARI	250
Ashurova Shaxnoza Almasovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARI KORXONALARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	257
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	262
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA MIJOZ QONIQLASHINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA	278
Aqsungul Usenova Tenel qizi, Qoraqalpoq davlat universiteti	
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzaboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	283
Azlarova Munira Muhammad-Amin qizi	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI SHAKLLANTIRISH, RIVOJLANTIRISH VA KO'RSATKICHLARINI O'RGANISH.....	289
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	
IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	294
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	299
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORI MUAMMOLARI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	304
Abdusalomov Ozodbek Baxtiyor o'g'li XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SERVIS XAVFSIZLIGI INDEKSI: SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA	311
Shodmanova Zubayda Ubaydullayevna O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI OSHIRISHDA AKT RIVOJLANISHINING O'RNI.....	315
Sadriddinov Ulug'bek Jaloliddin o'g'li QURILISH FAOLIYATI SOHALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.....	322
Xusanov Kamoliddin Xolmamat o'g'li INSON KAPITALI VA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI	326
Abdullo Sohibov SUN'YI INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	331
Davronov Sanjar Ziyotovich SUN'YI INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINI QABUL QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	336
Ashrapova Noilaxon Niyazxonovna ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI TAHLILI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	340
Ochilov Baxtiyor Muminjonovich THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IFRS AND FINANCIAL REPORTING.....	346
Tojiboyev Abdullajon Kamoliddin ugli SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	351
Astanakulov Olim Tashtemirovich Muxammad Id Balbaa (Muhammad Eid Balbaa) Habibe Elif Kutlugun (Habibe Elif Kutlugun) GLOBAL IQLIM O'ZGARISHI FONIDA EKOLOGIK SIYOSAT VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	357
Xamzayev Abdushukur Xudoyqulovich INTERNATIONAL MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR UZBEKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, AND ECONOMETRIC EVIDENCE.....	362
Aziz Kurbanovich Abdullaev Sarvarbek Allayev Erkin ugli Shavkat Asrolovich Ruziev DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	369
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTIDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI TAHLILI ("O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJ MISOLIDA).....	373
Barotov Baxtiyor Vaxobovich CHIQUINDILARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	377
Muxitdinova Kamola Alisherovna TRANSPORT LOGISTIKASIDA TAVAKKALCHILIKLARNI SUG'URTALASH: O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSH TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA TAQQOSIY TAHLIL.....	381
Jabborov Islom Xusan o'g'li YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI BARQAROR BOSHQARISH.....	385
Xayrullayev Shaxram Yunus o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SERVIS KORXONALARIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATI BOSHQARUVINING ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI	392
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich BIZNES JARAYONLARI MONITORINGI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA KO'RSATKICHLARI.....	398
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOT KONSEPSIYASINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARINI (INDIKATORLARINI) SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	403
Sharifxo'jayeva Xonzodaxon A'lo qizi TURIZM QISHLOQLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI TIZIMI	408
Xudaynazarova Dilorom NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUV VA BOSHQARUV HISOB TIZIMINING AMALIYOTI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	416
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich DAVLAT XARIDLARI JARAYONIDA XAVFLARNI IDENTIFIKATSIYA QILISH, TASNIFLASH VA RISKKA ASOSLANGAN ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	421
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich DEVELOPING GARMENT MANUFACTURING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	426
Mahbuba Rahmonova Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	430
Bakhit Mambetnazarov Atabek Tureev SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI VA MAJBURIY AJRATMALARNING DAVLAT MOLIYASIDAGI O'RNI: 2020-2025 YILLAR TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLI.....	434
Olimov Shukurulla Dilshodjon o'g'li ФАКТОРЫ ТЕКУЧЕСТИ КАДРОВ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	439
Джураева Гузаль Шавкатовна XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	447
Mamirov Zamir Uzoq o'g'li XORIJYIY TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHDA O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	453
Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich DAVLAT BYUDJETI XARAJATLARI HISOB VA TAHLILINING AMALDAGI TIZIMI	458
Ostonokulov Azamat Abduraimovich Tursinbaev Gafur Jolmurzaevich MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	464
Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich СТРАХОВАНИЕ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ СНИЖЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ПОТЕРЬ ОТ НЕПРЕДВИДЕННЫХ РИСКОВ, ОКАЗЫВАЮЩИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКУЮ ПРИБЫЛЬ (ДОХОД).....	470
Азимжон Мелиев Муродулло угли A STUDY ON THE COLLABORATIVE MECHANISM OF DIGITAL ARCHIVES GOVERNANCE AND TALENT GOVERNANCE: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON JOB COMPETENCY, PERFORMANCE EVALUATION, AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS	475
Wang Biao	

SANOAT KORXONALARI INNOVATSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	481
Bahodirov Shohruh Bahodir o'g'li	
QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORINI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING XALQARO TAJRIBASI.....	488
Mallabayev Jobir Baxtiyorovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY REPORTS OF OOO SAM TRADING STROY	493
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna	

ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY REPORTS OF OOO SAM TRADING STROY

Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna
Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of
Economics and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
Email: usmanova.dilfuza@mail.ru
ORCID: 0009-0008-9523-9853

Abstract: This article examines the theoretical foundations of financial reporting, the definition of the concept and functions of financial reporting, emphasizing its importance for business management. The main types of financial statements are considered, including the balance sheet, profit and loss statement and cash flow statement, and the efficiency of the enterprise is studied, including the analysis of asset turnover.

Keywords: Enterprise, market, investor, counterparties, efficiency, product, classification, auditor, income.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola moliyaviy hisobotning nazariy asoslarini ko'rib chiqadi, moliyaviy hisobot tushunchasi va funktsiyalarini belgilaydi, uning biznesni boshqarish uchun ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. U moliyaviy hisobotlarning asosiy turlarini, shu jumladan balans, daromadlar to'g'risidagi hisobot va pul oqimi to'g'risidagi hisobotni o'rganadi. Shuningdek, u kompaniya faoliyatini, shu jumladan aktivlar aylanmasini tahlil qilishni o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Korxonalar, bozor, investor, kontragentlar, samaradorlik, mahsulot, tasnif, auditor, daromad.

Анотация: В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические основы финансовой отчетности, определение понятия и функций финансовой отчетности, подчеркивающих ее значимость для управления бизнесом, Рассмотрены основные виды финансовых отчетов, включая баланс, отчет о прибылях и убытках и отчет о движении денежных средств, изучена эффективность деятельности предприятия, включающая анализ оборачиваемости активов.

Ключевые слова: Предприятие, рынок, инвестор, контрагенты, эффективность, товар, классификация, аудитор, доход.

INTRODUCTION

Financial statement analysis is an integral part of the management process for any organization, regardless of its size or industry. In today's market economy, where competition is becoming global and economic risks are growing, understanding and correctly interpreting financial indicators are essential tools for making informed management decisions. Effective management of a company's cash flows, cost optimization, and assessment of financial stability and profitability are all impossible without regular and in-depth financial statement analysis.

Financial statements provide systematic information about an organization's financial position, its operating results, and changes in financial condition over a given period. They serve as the basis for internal analysis and control, as well as for interaction with external stakeholders, such as investors, creditors, counterparties, and government agencies. For company management, financial statement analysis helps promptly identify weaknesses in financial performance and take action to address them. For external users, they provide a means of assessing the organization's financial strength and solvency, which is essential when making decisions about lending, investing, or entering into long-term contracts.

Based on international experience, it should be noted that a company's competitiveness in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its marketing policy. Many economists have developed marketing principles and applied them practically, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, and D. Marshall. These include such renowned scholars as F. Marshall.

It's worth noting the scholars who have made significant contributions to the development of marketing theory, although research conducted in the field of marketing in our country over many years has been based on national characteristics. These include R. Ibragimov, Yu. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodzhaeva, Sh. Ergashkhodzhaeva, Sh. Musaeva, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass observation methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and Results. The analysis and interpretation of a company's financial performance primarily depends on the analysis of its financial statements. In this coursework, I demonstrated an analysis of the financial position of SAM TRADING STROY LLC based on two statements: the balance sheet and the income statement.

Table No. 1
Balance sheet of the enterprise LLC "Sam Trading Stroy" for three years from 2021 to 2023.

	2021	2022	2023
	sum, thousand	sum, thousand	sum, thousand
ASSETS			
Long-term assets			
Initial cost	602,308.70	1,663,666.81	1,519,568.05
Depreciation amount	90,657.97	200,038.66	265,210.23
Residual (book) value	511,650.73	1,463,628.15	1,254,357.82
Total long-term assets	511,650.73	1,463,628.15	1,254,357.82
Current assets			
Total inventory	562,448.36	570,875.03	531,771.68
Accounts receivable	827,324.70	936,255.89	1,013,094.21
Total cash	3,713.69	333,044.96	4,496.43
Total current assets	1,393,486.75	1,840,175.88	1,549,362.32
TOTAL ASSETS	1,905,137.48	3,303,804.03	2,803,720.14
---	---	---	---
LIABILITIES			
Sources of own funds			
Authorized capital	201,820.00	201,820.00	201,820.00
retained earnings	249,610.30	607,892.64	666,225.83
Total equity	451,430.30	809,712.64	868,045.83
Long-term liabilities	-	-	-
Current liabilities			
Current accounts payable	1,453,707.16	2,009,243.38	1,632,650.31
Short-term bank loans	-	484,848.00	303,024.00
Total current liabilities	1,453,707.16	2,494,091.38	1,935,674.31
TOTAL EQUITY AND LIABILITIES	1,905,137.46	3,303,804.02	2,803,720.14

I conducted this analysis in several stages to ensure a complete understanding. First, I defined these types of reports. Next, I presented a brief analysis that describes the main key points and the dynamics of financial performance over a three-year period.

At the end of this section, a full analysis of the financial activities of OOO "SAM TRADING STROY" was shown, using frequently used financial ratios.

Before diving into the balance sheet and other financial statements in detail, it's helpful to quickly review some important points.

Having analyzed the balance sheet, the following can be noted:

- *Growth of long-term assets.* In 2021, the total value of long-term assets amounted to 511,650.73 thousand soums, and in 2022 it increased to 1,463,628.15 thousand soums, which is 2.86 times more than the previous value.

Figure 1. Dynamics of long-term assets of LLC “Sam Trading Sstroy” for three years from 2021 to 2023.

- This change may indicate the opening of additional warehouses and distribution centers. In 2023, the value of long-term assets, unfortunately, fell by 14.3% and reached 1,254,357.82 thousand soums (see Figure No. 3).
- *Significant growth in working capital items.* Compared to 2021, accounts receivable increased by approximately 13%, while accounts payable increased by 38%. Inventories, meanwhile, increased slightly, by just 1.5%. For 2023, only accounts receivable increased even more, by 8% compared to 2022. Other parameters are declining (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Changes in inventories and accounts receivable of OOO “Sam Trading Sstroy” for three years from 2021 to 2023.

- *A temporary significant increase in cash balances.* Compared to 2021, the cash balance in 2022 increased from 3,713,690 soums to 333,044,960 soums, a whopping 90-fold increase. However, this increase was temporary. In 2023, the cash balance amounted to 4,496,430 soums, not far from the 2021 figure.
- *Demonstrable ability to borrow.* Comparing long-term assets to long-term debt indicates a company's ability to provide collateral for future borrowing. Potential lenders always consider the value of assets that can be pledged as collateral for loan claims. Lenders particularly value land and, to a lesser extent, buildings in this

regard. This approach is explained by the fact that these assets typically retain their market value. For example, as of 2022, the book value of long-term assets was 1,463,628,150 soums, while long-term borrowings were zero. Even including short-term bank loans, which amount to 484,848,000 soums, the value of long-term assets is still significantly higher.

The main objective of the audit of the financial performance report is to confirm the reliability of the presented indicators, the correctness of their formation in accordance with current regulations and the accounting policies of the organization.

Revenue from current activities (sales of products, performance of work, or provision of services) is recognized in the amount of accrued debt on the debit side of the settlement account, taking into account current prices and tariffs, as well as benefits provided in accordance with legislation. The auditor must verify that revenue is correctly classified as income from ordinary activities or other revenue.

The auditor recalculates the report indicators and reconciles the values in column 3 "For the reporting year" with the data in the General Ledger and the analytical accounting registers for income and expense accounts. This control ensures the reliability and accuracy of the reporting data.

All income and expenses that are material to the organization must be separately reported. In particular:

- ❖ Income that constitutes 5% or more of total income must disclose the corresponding portion of expenses;
- ❖ income from ordinary activities, if significant, is shown separately either in the report or in an appendix to it;
- ❖ Column 4 is filled in based on data for the same period of the previous year, with adjustments made in the event of changes in accounting policies or regulatory requirements.

Tax Indicator Review. The financial performance report includes new lines for calculating income tax:

- permanent tax liabilities;
- deferred tax liabilities;
- deferred tax assets;
- current expenses for income tax.

The auditor verifies the accuracy of these indicators' calculations and their compliance with accounting policies. Permanent tax assets arising from deductible permanent differences are also taken into account, even if they are not reflected in NAS No. 3.

To confirm reliability, it is important to ensure that the current period's data is comparable to similar data from the previous year. If significant changes occur, the auditor analyzes the reasons for these changes, such as accounting policy adjustments, legislative changes, or other regulations.

It's important to emphasize the principle of materiality, which requires that revenues and expenses be presented separately if they are material. The following requirements must be met when compiling the financial performance report's indicators: - when reflecting types of income, each of which individually accounts for 5% or more of the organization's total revenue for the reporting period, the report shows the portion of expenses corresponding to each type; - column 4 of the report is populated based on the data in column 3 of the report for the previous year.

Audit procedure	Contents of the check
Checking compliance with regulations	Verification of the compliance of the structure and content of the report with NAS No. 2 and NAS No. 3
Checking arithmetic calculations	Reconciliation of column 3 with the data of the General Ledger and analytical registers
Revenue recognition control	Checking the correct classification of income from ordinary activities and other income
The principle of materiality	Separate reflection of income and expenses if they are significant
Checking tax indicators	Control over the calculation of fixed and deferred taxes, current expenses on income tax

Figure 3. Dynamics of LLC revenue “Sam Trading Sroy” for three years from 2021 to 2023.

Figure 4. Net profit of LLC “Sam Trading Sroy” for three years from 2021 to 2023.

Operating profit, meanwhile, declined from 490.9 million soums in 2022 to 191.5 million soums in 2023. This indicates a significant increase in commercial and administrative expenses, which directly impact operating profit. This means that even with stable gross profit, the company’s increased internal costs (e.g., management, marketing, and logistics) are leading to a decline in operating results. This decline is due to the fact that cost of sales and operating expenses increased by more than revenue (Figure 8).

It can also be noted that due to a sharp increase in interest payments, net profit has decreased significantly, by more than 10 times.

CONCLUSION

The study confirmed that systematic financial statement analysis is an integral part of business management. It allows not only for monitoring current financial performance but also for developing strategies for further

development. Proper management of profitability, liquidity, efficiency, capital structure, and investments contributes to a company's competitiveness and long-term sustainability.

Thus, the results of this coursework confirm the importance of financial analysis for business management. Sam Trading Stroy LLC can use the obtained data to improve its operational efficiency, minimize financial risks, and ensure stable market growth.

REFERENCES:

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 166 of March 29, 2021.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The rule of law and protection of human interests are the key to the development of the country and the well-being of the people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 48 p.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a great future with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. - 488 p.
4. Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020 - People's Speech, January 26, 2020
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". policies in trade and service enterprises.
6. Musaeva Sh.A. (2022). Study of the organization of advertising activities of goods at JSC Samarkand Tea Packaging Plant. Science and Innovation, 1(A6), 185-192.
7. Musaeva, Sh.A. (2022). Prospects for the development of activities of Stekloplastik LLC in a market economy. Science and Innovation, 1(A6), 539-546.
8. Musaeva Sh. A. Marketing Research. Publishing and Creative Department of Textbooks, ZVAR-SEL LLC. Samarkand–2024
9. Musaeva Sh. A. Integrated Marketing Communications. Textbook. Publishing House "Mahorat", Samarkand - 2022.
10. Israilov B.I., Fayziev U.Sh., Ibragimov B.Zh. Accounting in business. - T.: "Innovatsion rivozhlanish nashriyot-matbaa uyi", 2021. - 156 p.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4 (2)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>